

ISic0519

I.Sicily inscription 0519

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object

base

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Autopsy

2015.11.12 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates**

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo Civico di Marsala

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1

: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2

: mm

Text

Edition: EDR080558

1. T (ito) Quarto

2. Masculo

3. T (iti) Quarti Cres

4. centinii · Q (ui) r (ina) ·

5. fil (io) dec (urioni) spl (endidissimae)

6. col (oniae) Aug (ustae) Lilib (itanorum) Lilybitanorum

7. q (uestori) p (ecuniae) p (ublicae) cur (atori) f (rumenti) p (ublici)

8. [---]

Apparatus

text derived originally from EDR

The letters QR at the end of the line are

smaller, and between interpuncts. Mommsen (CIL)

read CENTINI · EQR; the reading here is that of Marino and Forni, and appears better to reflect what is visible on the stone

Translation

Commentary

Forni, following the reading of Marino of line 4, argues that this an abbreviation for the tribal Quirina, of a form known only in Africa and Numidia, i.e. areas of Punic culture. On the basis that Lilybaeum is also such an area, he suggests the same model, namely an abbreviation showing semitic influence, omitting vowels (examples offered by Forni are, from Africa CIL 8.1686, 1737, 6117; I.L.Alg. 2.4361, 4758, 4919, 5343, 5908). Bivona, in Kokalos 26-27 (1980-81), 408 rejects this view. Fresh autopsy is perhaps required.

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taf.13a

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Photo by M. Metcalfe